

FAIRSFair

Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe

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Technology to support semantic interoperability

The original paper describing the FAIR principles carefully avoided choosing a single technology to implement them. It can be seen, however, that research communities that are currently the furthest along the road to implement interoperability for FAIR data have often chosen Linked Data technologies (recognized by abbreviations like RDF, OWL, SKOS, SPARQL). This is not because this solution is the only approach that could be taken, but because it has been under development for many years and is currently one of the few frameworks that

can make data unambiguously understandable. It is possible that the role played by Linked Data today could be played by another more powerful approach in the future, but Linked Data has the best potential for implementing FAIR interoperability at this moment.

The core of Linked Data (see Figure 1) is formed by the Resource Description Framework (RDF). All data represented in RDF is turned into so-called “semantic triples” that each contain a statement in the form of subject-predicate-object, each describing either a property of something (subject: “bird” predicate: “body temperature in degrees C” object: “41”) or a relation between two things (subject: “Alice” predicate: “Talks to” object: “Bob”). In order to make these statements machine readable in RDF, subjects and predicates are never just a character string, but always an Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI). The objects in an RDF triple can either be a IRI, literal or blank node, and if it is a literal then there are techniques to make sure it is well described; e.g. the language of a string is explicitly added. To represent knowledge, multiple RDF triples are put together in a network or “graph”.

Figure 1: [The Semantic Web Stack according to Wikipedia.](#) (2022)

IRIs have a central place as unique identifiers for subjects, predicates and objects in RDF. In the design of the Linked Data paradigm, a central assumption is that these IRIs are the unique identifiers of the concepts in the graph, and it is good practice to use IRIs that correspond to human-readable and/or machine-readable explanations of the concepts. IRIs, however, do not satisfy all requirements that are currently expected from PIDs. It is often quite easy to use PIDs when using Linked Data by replacing regular IRIs by IRIs that are formed by combining PIDs with their resolver on the World Wide Web. When creating FAIR

semantic artefacts it's good practice to use globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers.

A common misconception about Linked Data is that it requires all data to be represented as RDF. In fact, RDF is a very inefficient way of storing and processing many forms of dense data. The requirement that is placed upon us for interoperability is not that the data is all converted to RDF, but that someone *skilled in the field* would be able to set up an automated process to perform that conversion fully automatically. However, it should be noticed that if data must still be interoperable in 10 years, that either requires that there will still be people available at that time who are *skilled in the field*, or, alternatively, that the automated process for the conversion is actually built. In practice, dense tabular research data is often left as such, and combined with abstracted conclusions and metadata represented as RDF, see for example the Allotrope Framework (<https://www.allotrope.org/allotrope-framework>).

When using Linked Data, the IRIs for related things are stored in collections, which are named differently depending on the structure and how the relationships are described. They can be named as glossary, controlled vocabulary, thesaurus, ontology or data model. All of these can together be called "semantic artefacts".

Data represented in RDF differs from data that is traditionally represented in tables in two important ways:

1. RDF is relatively flexible: in contrast to objects described in a table, it is not required that each object described in RDF has values for the same set of properties. This makes it equally easy in RDF to describe one-to-one relationships as one-to-many relationships, whereas in tabular data one-to-one relationships can be expressed using columns in a table, but one-to-many relationships require the creation of multiple tables with explicit connections.
2. RDF assumes an "open world": In contrast to objects described in a table where an "empty box" could mean that the object does not have the corresponding property, in RDF the absence of a triple describing a property (as a simple example: an owner) can only mean that it is *unknown*. Someone else may describe that property elsewhere. If it is *known* that a value does *not* exist (e.g. we know that the object does not have an owner), that is a property that should be made explicit. The open world makes it very easy for anyone to build upon existing knowledge in RDF, whereas it is virtually impossible to "add a column" to an existing data table or "fill in empty values" for anyone except the maintainer of an existing tabular dataset.

Many of the complexities in the implementation of RDF arise from its flexibility. Software that uses the data often makes assumptions about a data structure. Tabular data makes this easy because it enforces this structure. For RDF, a structure is more difficult to guarantee, and data structure validation is provided separately. One modern example of a technique used for this is the Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL). SHACL writes simple statements (in RDF!) about data that describes the structure of that data. It allows matching a *data graph* with a *shapes graph*. This way, SHACL makes it possible to describe what properties and relationships the nodes in the graph must have and must not have, use this to filter the

graph, and raise an error when conditions are not met. If there is no error, software querying the graph can be sure that it satisfies the structure it needs.

There are different ways in which RDF data can be represented. The original RDF was an XML markup language that is very voluminous and hard to understand for humans. An RDF graph can also be represented in other ways, of which TTL (pronounced “Turtle” and easier to read by humans), and JSON-LD are popular. Conversion between the different representations is simple and does not lose any information, so the variety of formats does not introduce additional semantic interoperability problems.

Figure 2. The EOSC Interoperability Framework and semantic interoperability (Figure 11 in EOSC IF (2021) <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>)

The FAIR Data Point

The FAIR Data Point is an open source solution for creating a FAIR compliant REST API to expose metadata. As it follows the DCAT2 ontology it also enables exposing the data model in a machine readable format. It uses the above-mentioned RDF and SHACL formats. The FDP API specification provides a reference for a FAIR way to present data, which can be utilized as an example and starting point when planning how to implement the FAIR data principles. See further the [FAIR Data Point](https://specs.fairdatapoint.org/) (<https://specs.fairdatapoint.org/>)

The source code in its entirety contains a web client, a server with APIs and a triplestore. The metadata models are defined by customisable definitions written in the SHACL language. The web client allows an admin user to extend existing metadata models and create new metadata types to allow for custom resource descriptions. This means that achieving semantic interoperability takes deploying several further standards, e.g. common or domain specific metadata schemas and semantic artefacts. DCAT2 and the planned update DCAT3 offer good prerequisites for this. It's important that there is continuous and wide expert

discussion and information sharing on how to implement domain specific and other standards to ensure future interoperability.

The development server in Python can be found here [FAIR Data Point \(FDP\)](https://github.com/fair-data/fairdatapoint) (<https://github.com/fair-data/fairdatapoint>) and another version in Java is here: [GitHub - FAIRDataTeam/FAIRDataPoint](https://github.com/FAIRDataTeam/FAIRDataPoint).

Creating semantic artefacts

Semantic artefacts provide reference metadata. When creating semantic artefacts collaboration with the designated community is necessary. You should make the semantic artefacts as FAIR as possible. The recommendations on FAIR semantics (D2.8 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6276576>) explain how this can be done. The same document also contains other recommendations for good practice.

Figure 3. From list to formal ontology: a transformation path. (Figure 3 in Recommendations for FAIR Semantics (2022) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6276576>)

References

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FAIRSFAR D2.4 2nd Report on FAIR requirements for persistence and interoperability. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5356517>

FAIRSFAR D2.8 3rd set of Recommendations for FAIR Semantics. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6276576>

FAIRSFAR D2.9 2nd reference implementation of the data repositories features and client application. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6204055>

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